

IPERION HS

Social media & web report

This social media and web report summarizes visually data extracted from the IPERION HS website and social media (October 2022 - October 2023).

The report highlights strengths and weaknesses in the IPERION HS communication strategy and offers useful insight to identify the audience, monitor engagement and schedule targeted contents.

Welcome to Gentella Admin Theme

Total Users 2500
+6% From last Week

Average Time 1.51 Sec
-3% From last Week

Total Males 2,500
+34% From last Week

Total Females 4,567
+12% From last Week

Total Collections 2,315
+34% From last Week

Total Connections 7,325
+34% From last Week

Daily active users Sessions
All users vs users affected crash

Daily active users Sessions
All users vs users affected crash

Daily active users Sessions
All users vs users affected crash

- Settings
- Subscription
- Auto Renewal
- Achievements
- Auto Renewal
- Achievements

Account Balance:
€0.00EUR
€0.00EUR per month
Basic Subscription

www.iperionhs.eu

Italy - United States - United Kingdom - Spain - France - China -
Germany - Poland - Netherlands - Malta

Countries

Visitors

13.4K

Unique visitors

13.2K

Page views

74K

Sessions

25.7k

786

users registered

 0,6%

USER EXPERIENCE: customization

Average duration session

00:02:13

1	
2	(not set)
3	/
4	/iperion-hs-2nd-doctoral-summer-school-organized-on-july-17-21-2023
5	/iperion-hsaccess
6	/ctinhs_lecture-08
7	/dashboard

Landing pages

Audience Grow Rate percentage

It measures the speed at which your brand's following increases on social media.

98,5%

Channels

Devices

MOBILE
36,1%

TABLET
0,7%

PC
63,2%

Engagement
rate

57,88%

Engaged
sessions

14.8K

impact
social media
13,60%

↓ - 0,13%

Social media (mostly Facebook, but also Twitter and LinkedIn) drive users towards the events of IPERION HS (webinars, doctoral summer schools, calls, etc...)

Countries

Italy - Spain - Greece - Portugal - France - Malta - United Kingdom - Brazil - Egypt - Germany - Romania

Demographics

Demographics

Followers

1575

New followers

204

Post

205

Page
engagement

3k

Audience Grow Rate percentage

It measures the speed at which your brand's following increases on social media.

12,9%

Sentiment

Best options to post

Iperion HS
Published by Elisabetta Andreassi · 28 March · 🌐

The Iperion HS #MOLAB is currently at work in the tomb of Philip II in #Verghina, a location near Thessaloniki, Greece today but Macedonia in the ancient past. The tomb of Philip II, the father of Alexander the Great, was one of the most important discoveries of the twentieth century. Brought to light on 8 November 1977 by the Greek archaeologist Manolis Andronikos, the tomb yielded an extraordinary quantity of gold and ivory objects, as well as a painted frieze more than five meters long and more than one meter high, representing a complex hunting scene in the extensive royal reserves of Upper Macedonia. The MOLAB diagnostic interventions focus on the large painted frieze with the contribution of ISPC CNR Istituto di Scienze del Patrimonio Culturale using XRF mapping and XRD mapping, #CNRSCITEC using hyperspectral imaging, UV-VIS-NIR reflectance and fluorescence, FT-IR reflectance, and ISAAC Research Center of the Nottingham Trent University School of Science and Technology using remote sensing (Raman/LIF, VIS/NIR, UV/LIF) and remote SWIR hyperspectral imaging.

E-rihs.eu
EAA European Association of Archaeologists
Heritage Research Hub

[See Insights and Ads](#) [Boost post](#)

👍❤️ 48 1 comment 7 shares

Top reactions

Iperion HS
Published by Elisabetta Andreassi · 18 January · 🌐

#jobopportunity

Open position as a Research Scientist working on Hyperspectral imaging data acquisition and processing related aspects at Lasers for Art's Sake IESL - FORTH in Heraklion (Greece).
Deadline for application: February 10, 2023
<https://www.iesl.forth.gr/en/about/job-positions/202398367>
E-rihs.eu

[See Insights and Ads](#) [Boost post](#)

👍❤️ 20 22 shares

👍 Like 💬 Comment ➦ Share

Top shares

Top posts

34,2%

Amplification Rate percentage

"It is the rate at which your followers take your content and share it through their networks" (Avinash Kaushik, Google)

IPERION HS

Followers

1198

New followers

147

Posts

294

Shares

651

Audience Grow Rate percentage

It measures the speed at which your brand's following increases on social media.

12,3%

Sentiment

Top tweets

#HSAcademy #CurrentTopicsHS Lecture 08 by @danoflynn is now online! Watch it & learn more about #Xrayimaging in #heritagescience:

16.67% engagement rate

The FULL PROGRAMME of the 2nd #HSAcademy Training Camp in Telč has just been published! <http://bit.ly/3KoGtqD> 5 days of #heritagescience

15.96% engagement rate

Oct 21, 08:09

@ErihsIt

https://twitter.com/iperion_hs/status/1583101724

545650689

14.29% engagement rate

Top engagement

IPERION HS
@iperion_hs

Promote ...

2nd #HSAcademy #Training Camp is organized on June 26-30, 2023 at ITAM CAS of @CzechAcademy in Telč. Apply to learn complexity of #built heritage with relevant #heritagescience scientific techniques. Register at: bit.ly/3XqGfTn More info: bit.ly/3W7McUd @ErihsEu

2:06 PM · Jan 12, 2023 · 1,606 Views

View post engagements

IPERION HS
@iperion_hs

Promote ...

The Iperion HS #MOLAB at work in one of the most extraordinary archaeological sites discovered ever: the tomb of Philip II, the father of Alexander the Great, in #Verghina. Diagnostic interventions focus on the large painted frieze representing a complex hunting scene.

CNR Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche and 5 others

11:59 AM · Mar 28, 2023 · 2,820 Views

View post engagements

Top retweets

Top impressions

Top tweets

54,3%

Amplification Rate percentage

It is the rate at which your followers take your content and share it through their networks" (Avinash Kaushik, Google)

LinkedIn

Follower demographics ?

Created with mapchart.net

Location ▾

London Area, United Kingdom, United Kingdom · 93 (3.4%)

The Randstad, Netherlands, Netherlands · 86 (3.2%)

Greater Rome Metropolitan Area, Italy · 83 (3.1%)

Greater Paris Metropolitan Region, France · 73 (2.7%)

Greater Madrid Metropolitan Area, Spain · 61 (2.2%)

Cairo, Egypt · 58 (2.1%)

Greater Milan Metropolitan Area, Italy · 52 (1.9%)

Florence, Italy Metropolitan Area, Italy · 47 (1.7%)

Athens Metropolitan Area, Greece · 40 (1.5%)

Greater Turin Metropolitan Area, Italy · 38 (1.4%)

countries

Followers

2715

New followers

1400

Posts

178

Post shares

445

Audience Grow Rate percentage

It measures the speed at which your brand's following increases on social media.

51,6%

Heritage Science Online Forum
2,715 followers
3mo · 🌐

#HSAcademy - a joint initiative by IPERION HS and E-RIHS - offers a wide range of cutting-edge #training opportunities in #heritagescience. The most recent one is a Doctoral Summer School organized last week at ZAG Slovenija! We are happy to share some details about this event: read below 📖
We are looking forward to announcing new activities on:
<https://lnkd.in/dgyrRBzD>
Heritage Research Hub

Katja Malovrh Rebec · 2nd
Head of The Department and Laboratory for Building Physiol...
3mo · 🌐 [+ Follow](#)

🏆 IPERION HS Doctoral Summer School 2023 Concludes with Great Success! 🏆

As the IPERION HS Doctoral Summer School 2023 draws to a close today, I am thrilled to announce the great success of this enriching event! 📖 It has been an incredible journey of learning, collaboration, and inspiration in the realm of #HeritageScience and #CulturalHeritage. I extend my heartfelt gratitude to all the participants, speakers, and organizers who made this experience truly unforgettable. 🙌

🔍 **Event Highlights:**
Throughout the program, our talented attendees had the opportunity to dive deep into the latest research and advancements in Heritage Science. From captivating lectures delivered by prominent academics to hands-on workshops where participants honed their skills, this summer school has been a catalyst for fostering innovative ideas in heritage preservation and conservation.

🌐 **International Network:**
The IPERION HS Doctoral Summer School brought together researchers from diverse backgrounds and regions, creating a global network of passionate individuals committed to safeguarding our rich cultural heritage. The connections made during this event will undoubtedly lead to valuable collaborations and impactful contributions to the field.

👏 **Acknowledging Our Attendees:**
We extend a special thanks to all the dedicated attendees who actively participated and contributed their expertise to the vibrant discussions and collaborative projects. Your enthusiasm and commitment to advancing Heritage Science are truly commendable! 🙌

🙌 **Gratitude to Organizers:**
My heartfelt appreciation goes out to the IPERION HS team (especially to [Matija Strlic](#), [Recco Mazzeo](#), [Jana Striova](#) and [Antonina Chaban](#)) and all the ZAG team who worked tirelessly to curate an exceptional learning experience. Your dedication and hard work made this summer school a resounding success. Thank you: [Tadeja Kosec](#), [Katja Zagar](#), [Andreja Pondetak](#), [mateja Golez](#), [@andraz legat](#), [@anja lesek](#) and all others.

🎉 **Let's Celebrate!**

#HeritageScience #CulturalHeritage #SuccessCelebration #GratitudePost #IPERIONHS #DoctoralSummerSchool #HeritagePreservation #Conservation #AcademicCommunity

Antonina Chaban and 12 others

Reactions
+5

👍 Like 💬 Comment 🔄 Repost ➦ Send

Add a comment...

Heritage Science Online Forum
2,715 followers
9mo · 🌐

#jobopportunity
Position open as a Research Scientist working on Hyperspectral imaging data acquisition and processing related aspects at Lasers for Art's Sake IESL - FORTH in Heraklion (Greece).
Deadline for application: February 10, 2023
<https://lnkd.in/dqhWYJcx>

Emanuela Grifoni and 90 others
19 reposts

Reactions
+83

👍 Like 💬 Comment 🔄 Repost ➦ Send

Top shares

Top engagement

Top posts

Heritage Science Online Forum
2,715 followers
10mo · 🌐

Check your interest in the **ICCROM** international course on "Managing World Heritage" and apply before January 27, 2023!
#heritage, #training

ICCROM
30,252 followers
10mo · 🌐

We are seeking 20 participants to join the international course on Managing World Heritage: People Nature Culture that will be held online in English from 13 to 23 February 2023.

This flagship foundational course of the World Heritage Leadership Programme is dedicated to site coordinators, members of management teams and institutions, and heritage practitioners working with World Heritage properties and other heritage places around the world.

Apply by 27 JAN 2023 📄 <https://bit.ly/3C5T11f>

Organized by **#ICCROM**, **IUCN**, @Cultural Heritage Administration of Korea (CHA), Korea National University of Cultural Heritage (KNUCH), Instituto Regional del Patrimonio Mundial en Zacatecas and **Klima- og miljødepartementet**

#worldheritageleadership #worldheritagesite #PNC #pnc23 #peoplenatureculture #management #leadership #culture #people #university #people #administration

CALL FOR APPLICATIONS
Managing World Heritage: People Nature Culture
ONLINE | 13-23 FEBRUARY 2023

Apply until 27 Jan 2023 **APPLY NOW**

Pedro De Campos and 34 others
1 comment

Top impressions

16,4%

Amplification Rate percentage

It is the rate at which your followers take your content and share it through their networks (Avinash Kaushik, Google)

 Website

 Facebook

 LinkedIn

Google

786

Facebook

1575

Twitter

1198

Linkedin

2715

Users: numbers

+1751 new followers
on social media
and +317 new users registered
in the website in the last year

Google

98,5%

Facebook

12,9%

Twitter

12,3%

Linkedin

51,6%

Audience Grow Rate Percentage

It is the rate at which
your followers take
your content and
share it through their
networks

(Avinash Kaushik, Google)

Facebook

34,2%

Twitter

54,3%

Linkedin

16,4%

Amplification Rate Percentage

#HeritageScience

Mentions

Reach

IAPERION HS: a relevant legacy

Overview

Export to CSV

	e-rihs	iperion hs
Total mentions ⓘ	43	43
Social media mentions ⓘ	3	26 ★
Non-Social media mentions ⓘ	40 ★	17
Positive mentions ⓘ	3% (1)	14% (6) ★
Negative mentions ⓘ	0% (0)	0% (0)
Social media reach ⓘ	4934	41K ★
Non-Social media reach ⓘ	114K ★	25K
Presence score ⓘ	5/100	6/100 ★
AVE ⓘ	\$ 9544 ★	\$ 4979
User generated content ⓘ	3	26 ★

Overview

Export to CSV

	e-rihs	heritagescience
Total mentions ⓘ	43 ★	34
Social media mentions ⓘ	3	33 ★
Non-Social media mentions ⓘ	40 ★	1
Positive mentions ⓘ	3% (1)	24% (8) ★
Negative mentions ⓘ	0% (0)	0% (0)
Social media reach ⓘ	4934	86K ★
Non-Social media reach ⓘ	114K ★	19
Presence score ⓘ	5/100 ★	3/100
AVE ⓘ	\$ 9544 ★	\$ 6545
User generated content ⓘ	3	32 ★

The most influential

The most active

Top public profiles

The most influential sites

HertSci_UK	★ 40.2% VOICE SHARE	📶 34 616 INFLUENCE
iperion_hs	★ 24.6% VOICE SHARE	📶 21 200 INFLUENCE
Scottish3D	★ 9.5% VOICE SHARE	📶 8200 INFLUENCE
lucianoor_m	★ 4.9% VOICE SHARE	📶 4200 INFLUENCE
ErihsEu	★ 4.2% VOICE SHARE	📶 3606 INFLUENCE

IPERION HS Social Media & Web Report
(October 2022-October 2023)
Authors: Laura Benassi & Antonina Chaban
Year: October 2023

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